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Effectiveness of Project-Based Entrepreneurship Learning Methods for High School Students

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Abstract

Entrepreneurship in Indonesia still needs to be encouraged again, so that the number of entrepreneurs increases. Project-based learning is an alternative method that requires practice which can have a big impact on students. Senior high schools (SMA) should be able to provide greater practical content in entrepreneurship subjects. The method used is the experimental method, pretest post test. The research results show that project-based methods can improve entrepreneurship learning outcomes in high school students.

Keywords: *effectiveness, project-based, entrepreneurship*

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INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship formation programs in Indonesia have been going on for quite a long time, carried out in formal and non-formal institutions. This entrepreneurship formation program is carried out independently or in partnership with the support of government funds or donor agencies which allocate a budget every year for entrepreneurship programs, especially for unemployed teenagers. However, these programs are not enough to lead to the emergence of new entrepreneurs. To make this happen, one thing that must be improved is infrastructure and connectivity Adam, L. (2016). Plus, we must continue to develop human resources and an entrepreneurial spirit. Some of the things that are carried out in developing an entrepreneurial spirit are expanding the National Entrepreneurship Movement throughout Indonesia, implementing an entrepreneurship curriculum from basic education to tertiary education, creating innovative SMEs through the role of business and technology incubators in accordance with Presidential Decree 27/2013 concerning entrepreneurial incubators. Furthermore, by organizing various activities to increase entrepreneurship for existing and newly growing SMEs. In high school circles by developing students' entrepreneurial spirit and facilitating entrepreneurial activities. At the high school level. High school students need very applicable methods, such as project-based methods (Suryadi, 2018).

The projects used are also varied, tailored to students' interests. This aims to encourage the growth of entrepreneurial motivation in students so that in the future they have the courage to open new businesses, even in the form of UKM (Small and Medium Enterprises) but are able to open up job opportunities for many people (Sulasari, 2016). Development of Project-Based Entrepreneurship Learning Methods to Improve Student Entrepreneurial Character at Malang State Polytechnic. Business & Management Accounting (ABM), 23(1), 16-28.. From the educational process, it is hoped that students will also be able to provide assistance to MSME actors in city or village areas. One of the high schools that still applies project-based entrepreneurship learning is YADIKA High School in Tangerang. Researchers are interested in examining the effectiveness of project-based learning. The aim of the research is to determine the effectiveness of project-based learning in high school students.

METODE

This research uses a type of experimental research, a pre-experimental design research method with a one-group pre-test-post-test design type. experimental method with a pre-Experimental method

design type one-group pre-test-post-test design is an experimental method carried out by only one treatment or one group without any comparison group. The following is a pre-experimental research method design with a one-group pre-test-post-test design type.

Table 1. Disain eksperimen

O1	X	O2
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Information :

X = Treatment (project method)

O1 = Pre-test (before treatment)

O2 = Post-test (after treatment)

Data is taken by means of tests and documentation. The data was processed using SPSS version 25. The data was tested for normality and homogeneity of the data as well as the paired sample t test. The data that has been processed will be concluded. Jumlah responden sebanyak 35 siswa kelas XI IPA SMA Yadika.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After carrying out the project-based method, students are given a test to determine the effectiveness of the project-based learning method. or images must be numbered and referred to in the text. The following are the results of SPSS 25 data processing.

Case Processing Summary

Kelas	Valid		Missing		Total			
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent		
Hasil Belajar kewirausahaan	Postes		35	100.0%	0	0.0%	35	100.0%
	pretes		35	100.0%	0	0.0%	35	100.0%

The results show that the respondents were 35 students. All data is processed. Both pretest and posttest data. After going through the above process, the data is again processed for normality and homogeneity tests, the results are,

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk				
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.		
Hasil Belajar siswa	pretest		.272	30	.000	.773	35	.000
	Postest		.172	30	.023	.943	35	.109

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Test of Homogeneity of Variance

		Levene			Sig.
		Statistic	df1	df2	
Hasil Belajar siswa	Based on Mean	5.485	1	58	.023
	Based on Median	4.910	1	58	.031
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	4.910	1	46.945	.032
	Based on trimmed mean	5.462	1	58	.023

In the Normality assumption test there is a Shapiro wilk sig value. $0.773 > 0.005$ which means the data is normally distributed. Likewise with the Kolmogorov value of $0.272 > 0.005$ which means the data is normally distributed. In the homogeneity table, there is a Sig value > 0.005 . Sig value. $0.023 > 0.005$ which means the data comes from homogeneous data. Data can be continued in the t sample paired test.

		Paired Samples Test							
		Paired Differences							
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
Paired Samples 1	Sebelum	-	6.1109	1.11570	-	-	-	29	.000
	Sesudah	17.36667	5		19.64853	15.08480	15.566		

In the Paired sample test table, the sig value. $0.000 < 0.005$ which means there is a difference in pretest and posttest scores. Based on the data above, it can be concluded that the effectiveness of the projet method can improve the entrepreneur's outcome.

DISCUSSION

The effectiveness test results of the Entrepreneurship learning module were obtained based on pretest and posttest scores from students after carrying out various projects, ranging from catfish breeding, motorbike servicing, and culinary businesses in several groups of students in the effective category (Siagian, et al, 2020). The developed project-based Entrepreneurship learning module can be used in the learning process to improve learning outcomes of students Natalia, W., & Jalinus, N. (2021). In general, students' characters prefer guidance in learning, and like the challenges provided in the learning process. By analyzing the characteristics of students, researchers can determine the right approach to apply in the learning process Manik, S. M. (2020).

The products produced by student work groups are in accordance with their learning styles. The effectiveness test shows that project-based entrepreneurship learning has been able to foster students' entrepreneurial spirit very well Lugiati, L. (2020). This type of project-based teaching is a form of implementing education that is creative and centered on students and positions the teacher as a liaison and motivator in teaching. Students are given the opportunity to design learning and carry out practice independently. Project-based learning has a very positive influence on efforts to increase students' enthusiasm and entrepreneurial spirit (Marten, D., & Syah, N. (2019). This can be seen from the answers given by students, 84.6% or at strong category. Currently students are more enthusiastic about carrying out projects because they get income from the results of the projects they work on. Ubaidillah, M. (2017). Besides that, it will also have an impact on their entrepreneurial values getting better (Sunaryo, 2023).

The implementation of production units in schools can also help students to practice their skills as well as foster the enthusiasm and entrepreneurial spirit of the students themselves (Suhartatik, 2018). The spirit of entrepreneurship must always be taught and developed in schools so that students have changing mindsets according to the challenges of today's times. The technological leap in the 4.0 era has brought rapid changes to the world of vocational education while also providing opportunities to train students' entrepreneurial spirit.

CONCLUSION

Project-based learning, helps students get to know each other more closely. Project practice can also realize and bring students closer to two real endeavors. Effectiveness test results show that project-based learning can improve entrepreneurial learning outcomes.

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